

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 11

Acceptance of papers **November, 2025**

**Acceptance of
papers**

Published monthly

Topics

economics,
technology, social
sciences

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Electronic publication, Issue 11. 166 pages.
Approved for publication on November, 2025.

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CONTENTS

POVERTY AND DEVELOPMENT	14
Kholmirezayev Abdulhamid Khapizovich	
WAYS TO ACHIEVE ECONOMIC STABILITY THROUGH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.....	23
Sadriddinov Bakhtiyor	
STRUCTURE-PROPERTY RELATIONSHIP OF ORGANOSILICON MATERIALS: EVALUATION BASED ON THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS	36
Tosheva Dilfuza Farxodovna, Siddikov Ikrom Iminjonovich, Rakhimov Firuz Fazlidinovich	
"CREATING AN ALGORITHM AND SOFTWARE TOOL FOR PERSONAL IDENTIFICATION USING FACIAL SCANNING TO PROTECT THE OPERATING SYSTEM"	43
Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li	
ENSURING INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION BASED ON MOBILE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES.....	51
Zaripov Olimjan Kuvandiq son	
MONITORING OF THE AYDAR-ARNASAY LAKE SYSTEM AND ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF COLLECTOR WATER INFLOWS INTO THE LAKE ECOSYSTEM.....	55
Erkabayev Furkat Ilyasovich, Madrimov Rajabboy Masharipovich, Aminov Khamza Khusanovich	
APPROBATION OF THE RESISTANCE OF BRICKS MADE FROM "ANGREN" SECONDARY KAOLIN TO THE EFFECT OF LIQUID METAL.....	62
Umurov Ulug'bek Meylievich	
THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PERFORMANCE-BASED BUDGETING.....	68
Allakuliev Akmal Baltayevich	
IMPROVING ECONOMIC MECHANISMS THROUGH EFFECTIVE USE OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS IN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT.....	71
Abdusalomov Djamshid Abdusalomovich	
TEMPERATURE-RADIATION REGIME OF THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN FOR THE DESIGN OF SOLAR GREENHOUSES	76
Ilkhom Ismatovich Rakhmatov, Shakhzod Niyoz ogli Izomov	
THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF GREEN FINANCING IN FORMING A GREEN ECONOMY	81
Khalikov S. X.	
MUVAFFAQIYATLI STARTAP FAOLIYATIDA ROL O'YNOVCHI MUHIM OMILLAR VA O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA STARTAP EKOTIZMINING RIVOJLANISHI.....	87
Qosimova Dilorom Sobirovna	
EFFECTIVENESS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS.....	92
Umarova Nilufar Abdulkakhorkizi	
INFLUENCE OF INTERNATIONAL RANKING ORGANIZATIONS ON HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND EXISTING PLATFORMS	96
Urozboev Khayrulla Murodboy ugli	
BASE STATION MONITORING TECHNOLOGIES IN MOBILE NETWORKS	103
Ibrokhimkhuja Rikhsikhujayev, Mohit Bhandwal	
FORMATION AND MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS OF ENTERPRISES	108
Abdunazarov Saidakhmat Abdumalikovich	
THE IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISE ACTIVITY MANAGEMENT.....	113
Rasulov Shavkat Sharof son	
PARTICIPATORY BUDGETING OF THE STATE BUDGET	117
Khamidov Khabibullo Khikmatulla ogli	
TRANSFORMING THE HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR THROUGH PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP UNDER CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION	123
Abdullayev Javohir Abdumalik og'li	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN ENTERPRISES.....	131
Begalov Sherzod Maxsutaliyevich	

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE RESERVOIR SAFETY ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE TALIMARJON RESERVOIR.....	136
Xodjaqulova Nodira Xosiyatqul qizi	
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY AND INNOVATIVE TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION IN UZBEKISTAN'S OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY	141
Tarakhtiyeva Gulmira Kulbayevna	
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO RISK MANAGEMENT AND ASSESSMENT OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	145
Muxitdinova Kamola Alisherovna	
INNOVATIVE COOPERATION AND MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR STRENGTHENING THE REGIONAL ECONOMY: THE CASE OF NAMANGAN REGION	149
Sattarov R. A.	
MARKETING PROBLEMS IN THE INTERNATIONAL TEXTILE MARKET AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN SOLVING THEM.....	159
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	

MARKETING PROBLEMS IN THE INTERNATIONAL TEXTILE MARKET AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN SOLVING THEM.

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Abstract: This article examines the market position of the textile industry by country, the promotion of the textile industry in all countries, support for the textile industry in Asian countries, and the study and application of the positive experience of foreign countries to help the textile industry of Uzbekistan find its place in the world market.

Key words: Market, foreign experience, textiles, experience, export, innovation.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mamlakatlar bo'yicha to'qimachilik sanoatini bozordaga o'rni, barcha davlatlarda to'qimachilik sanoatini rag'batlantirish, Osiyo davlatlarida to'qimachilik sanoatini qo'llab-quvvatlash, O'zbekiston to'qimachilik sanoatini jahon bozorida o'z o'rnini topishi uchun xorijiy mamlakatlarning ijobiy tajribasini o'rganish va qo'llash ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bozor, xorijiy tajriba, to'qimachilik, tajriba, eksport, innovatsiya.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается место текстильной промышленности на рынке по странам, продвижение текстильной промышленности во всех странах, поддержка текстильной промышленности в странах Азии, а также изучение и применение положительного опыта зарубежных стран для содействия текстильной промышленности Узбекистана в её выходе на мировой рынок.

Ключевые слова: Рынок, зарубежный опыт, текстиль, опыт, экспорт, инновации.

INTRODUCTION

The textile industry is a constantly growing market, and its main competitors are China, the European Union, the United States and India. China is the world's leading producer and exporter of textiles and clothing. The United States is the leading producer and exporter of raw cotton and the largest importer of textiles and clothing. The European Union's textile industry includes Germany, Spain, France, Italy and Portugal, which together account for more than 1/5 of the world's textile industry.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

In increasing national competitiveness The analysis of the available literature shows the need to improve modern market principles, brand promotion methods and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on market strategies, the expert RGIbragimov states the following: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of the enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success." Many economists have been involved in the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R.Ibragimov, YO.Abdullaev, A.Saliev, M.Sharifkhodjaev, D.Rakhimova, Sh.Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh.Musayeva and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results. Global Market Insights, an analytical agency, published a report, according to which the global smart textile market was worth \$2.147 billion in 2021, and by 2030 this figure will grow to \$16.4 billion. Based on other sources, the size of this market in 2024 will be \$1.94 trillion, and is forecast to reach \$4.91 trillion in 2037 (Figure 1).

As can be seen from this figure, cotton products occupy the largest share in the textile market (40%), and within regions, Asia-Pacific countries are one of the main segments of the manufacturer's market (52%).

China, in 2024, China is the world's largest textile producer and exporter. It occupies more than 30% of the global market and exports its products to more than 200 countries and regions.

Figure 1. Size and structure of the world textile market¹

According to the World Trade Organization (WTO) reports, the leading countries in the production and export of textile products include: India, which specializes in the production of cotton, woolen fabrics and silk; Netherlands. Dutch textile manufacturers widely use digital printing and innovative dyeing methods; United Kingdom, which exports wool, silk, cotton, synthetic materials and special fabrics for various industries; Spain. Cotton, wool, linen, silk and synthetic fabrics from Spain enter the world markets; Pakistan. The country has large reserves of cotton, which makes it one of the leading countries in the production of cotton materials; Sri Lanka. The country specializes in the production and export of high-quality textile materials, including cotton, silk, synthetic, linen and woolen fabrics.

At the same time, due to the strong competition in the world market of textile and garment and knitwear products, the leaders of the product market are constantly changing. Based on the study of the factors that ensure the market position of the textile industry in each country, large-scale activities are being carried out in all countries to stimulate the textile industry. This policy is especially evident in the Asian region. Analysis shows that support for the textile industry in Asian countries is mainly aimed at supporting small and medium-sized

¹ <https://www.researchnester.com/ru/reports/textile-market/6181>

businesses, especially microenterprises. In order for the textile industry of Uzbekistan to find its place in the world market, it is advisable to study and apply the positive experience of foreign countries. We have examined the state policy of supporting the textile industry on the example of some countries.

People's Republic of China. The share of the garment and textile industry in China's total GDP exceeds 11%. Tax revenues from the textile and garment industry allow China to generate up to 15-20% of the country's budget. The textile and garment industry occupies the largest share of light industry sub-sectors, contributing every fifth yuan to the Chinese budget. Currently, about 400,000 different clothing brands are produced in China, of which about 50% are foreign.

China's light industry policy includes the following measures:

- establishment of a special state fund to support small and medium-sized businesses;
- establish a preferential tax regime for;
- implementation financial and credit support;
- of small businesses ensuring access to the distribution of government orders;
- implementation of other incentive events.

If we focus on specific measures in the textile industry, the following areas of support for enterprises in this sector in China can be highlighted:

- 1) establish a special state fund to support small and medium-sized businesses;
- 2) ensuring the possibility of small businesses to benefit from the distribution of government orders (SMEs will be allocated at least 30 percent of the annual budget for government procurement);
- 3) a mechanism to support both small and medium-sized businesses themselves and the structures that guarantee the repayment of loans granted to them
- 4) export support: a constant increase in the tax refund rate for many types of exported light industrial products (garment, textiles, etc.);
- 5) allocation of funds for the modernization of production technologies;
- 6) Measures will be taken to encourage enterprises that move production capacity from southeastern China to central and western regions;
- 7) expanding urban and rural consumption and increasing the efficiency of supplying light industrial products to the domestic market;
- 8) improving foreign trade services, maintaining the share of light industrial products in the export market.

India. India is the only country that produces 4 types of silk. India ranks second in the world after China with 34.9 thousand tons of silk production. The textile and garment industry accounts for 2.3 percent of the country's GDP, 13 percent of industrial output, and 12 percent of exports. The Indian textile and garment market is expected to grow at an average annual rate of 10 percent to reach \$ 350 billion by 2030, and the industry's share in India's GDP is expected to double to 5 percent. This trend is widespread across all industry sectors, with the technical textiles market for the automotive industry expected to grow from \$ 2.4 billion in 2020 to \$ 3.7 billion by 2027.

Today, India is the world's third largest exporter of textiles and apparel and the fifth largest market for technical textiles globally, according to IBEF. Exports were valued at \$36 billion in 2024, accounting for 12% of India's total export earnings.

Government-supported programs include programs that encourage the localization of textile production and exports. Make in India and Aatmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan enters. Skill India provides subsidies to educational institutions to create specialized programs. There is a special program to support the technical textile industry, the National Technical Textile Mission.

Nine Councils have been established in India to promote textile exports. Each Council promotes a specific type of product and monitors the sales opportunities of Indian goods. Various mechanisms and funds have been established to provide government assistance to textile enterprises:

Technology Upgradation Fund Scheme (TUFS) to provide government compensation and subsidies to manufacturers;

The role of the government under the Integrated Textile Parks Scheme (SITP) is to establish these technology parks;

Introduce the «Mega Cluster Development» scheme to support weavers and artisans in home-based industries;

Integrated Skills Development Scheme (ISDS) to upskill workers in the textile industry.

Today, the government is promoting the establishment of specialized industrial zones by providing tax breaks and subsidies to enterprises operating in the regions. For example, in August 2023, the government will provide seven special industrial zones for new and existing enterprises. PM Integrated Textile and Garment Park (PMMITRA) approved the creation. According to IBEF, these parks will have world-class infrastructure by 2027–2028, involving an investment of \$535 million.

Bangladesh. The textile industry is a major sector in Bangladesh, with 3,500 garment factories in the country. Bangladesh plays a significant role in the global textile and garment trade and is a key link in the global textile supply chain.

Bangladesh's textile and garment industry forms the backbone of the country's economy and contributes significantly to the global market.

Information about the country's role in the textile market: production of clothing for major international brands. In Bangladesh Adidas, Levi's, Calvin Klein, Zara, H&M and other brands are manufactured. Export of ready-made garments. By the end of December 2024, the Bangladeshi garment industry earned \$50 billion from exports, an increase of 8.3 percent compared to the previous year. The dominance of ready-made garments in the country's export trade. Dependence of global brands on Bangladeshi factories. Large international companies largely depend on Bangladeshi factories to meet their production needs.

The textile industry is an important sector of the Bangladeshi economy for several reasons:

- Exports of textiles and garments are a major source of foreign exchange earnings. According to the country's Export Promotion Bureau (EPB), the garment industry in Bangladesh earned \$50 billion in export earnings by the end of December 2024, an increase of 8.3 percent over the previous year;
- Availability of cheap labor. High population density provides cheap labor for the industrial sector. This has a positive impact on the cost of production;
- The development of enterprises producing various types of products. Many factories specialize in the production of knitted fabrics, woven fabrics, and yarns;
- Experience in the industry. The country has been developing industry since the mid-1970s, and the textile industry has made a significant contribution to it. In recent years, specialization in the textile industry has become an important part of the country's strategy;
- Employment opportunities for women. The garment sector has provided employment for rural women who previously did not have the opportunity to be part of the formal workforce. The garment industry accounts for more than 80% of Bangladesh's total export earnings and contributes about 11% of the country's GDP. Its exports have grown from \$5 billion in 2001 to nearly \$40 billion in 2023.

Pakistan Pakistan is one of the largest textile countries, exporting \$31 billion worth of textile products annually, mainly to European and US markets, and has a well-developed textile industry. The country's GSP+ system is also present, integrated into the global value chain and supplying products to famous brands. This is the largest segment of the country's light industry and one of the largest in the world.

The textile industry accounts for 8.5 percent of Pakistan's GDP. Textile exports account for a significant portion of the country's total exports. The textile industry employs about a third of the country's industrial workforce.

Pakistan is one of the largest textile producers in Asia for several reasons:

Own raw material base. The bulk of the materials used in the textile industry (cotton fiber, wool, finished fabrics) are produced in Pakistan itself. This ensures low production costs and their competitiveness in the world market.

Production capacity. The country has cotton ginning and spinning factories, large and small textile and garment factories.

Variety of products manufactured. Pakistan's textile enterprises export cotton, wool, linen, silk, and synthetic fabrics of various colors, textures, and patterns.

Specialized knowledge and expertise. Pakistan has accumulated specialized knowledge in the production of functional textiles, including silver fibers.

Vietnam. More than seven thousand enterprises operate in the textile and garment industry in Vietnam, employing more than three million people. More than 80% of the output is exported - in 2023, clothing exports amounted to about 44 billion US dollars, an increase of 11.26% compared to the previous year. At the same time, Vietnam's textile industry is closely linked to external factors, as a result of which a sharp decline in exports was observed in 2024. To support the textile industry and stop the decline in exports, the state is taking the following measures: creating material and financial conditions for the use of new, highly productive technologies in textile enterprises, taking measures to reduce internal costs, creating conditions for exporters, and attracting foreign investment to the sector.

European Union States. State support for industry in the European Union countries is horizontal in nature, including economic measures and regulatory measures, and does not apply specifically to the light industry sector.

At the same time, macroeconomic measures of state support for industry, including light industry, include: improving tax policy (including tax breaks and simplifications); improving monetary policy (granting credit benefits); improving customs policy (benefits for foreign investments in light industry enterprises); supporting exports (export credits and state guarantees); creating business infrastructure and improving cooperation within the European Union.

At the micro level, this is, first of all, support for small and medium-sized enterprises, including policies to stimulate competition, eliminate administrative barriers, improve access to financial resources, preferences for the export of goods and capital, and support in foreign markets.

If we consider Spain, a country with a developed textile and clothing industry, the turnover of the country's enterprises in 2024 was around 49-50 billion euros, and the direct value added was reached 9.2–9.5 billion euros. The sustainable development of the Spanish textile industry is based on the following factors:

-sustainable raw materials: expanding the use of environmentally friendly, recycled raw materials in production, such as recycled cotton, raw materials from recycled plastic waste, silk and wool based on sustainable standards, etc.;

-focusing the production process on maximum efficiency. In the implementation of ISO 14001 environmental management systems in textile enterprises, scientific and technological innovations are being introduced aimed at saving increasingly expensive energy resources, reducing waste, and reducing the consumption of water and other natural resources.

Today, trends in the Spanish textile industry include the introduction of a circular economy, reducing carbon emissions, optimizing cost management and product delivery, and promoting technological development.

The experience of the above countries shows that today, state support for the textile industry is becoming one of the main drivers for overcoming competitors in the global market.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The textile and garment and knitwear industry occupies one of the leading positions in the economy of our country. Its share in the manufacturing industry is about 17% and is considered one of the sectors with high export potential. The textile and garment and knitwear industry also makes a significant contribution to the fulfillment of major tasks such as deep processing of local agricultural products and providing jobs for the population.

The textile and garment and knitwear industry has a number of unique features and requires systematic support from the state to ensure its sustainable competitiveness in the global market. From 2019 to the present, the President of our country has created a favorable environment for investments in the sector, providing incentives to manufacturers, and creating international logistics systems.

The uniqueness of the products of the textile and garment-knitting industry, as well as the characteristics of enterprises in the sector, have a significant impact on the content and structural elements of marketing activities.

It was found that the classification of textile and sewing and knitting enterprises can be carried out according to the following characteristics: type of enterprise, type of market, market position. In particular, it was found that all enterprises can be divided into three large groups: enterprises for the production of yarn and thread (IK), textiles (T) and ready-made sewing and knitting products (TT). By type of market, enterprises are focused on the consumer market, the enterprise market and the foreign market. The market position of the enterprise can be high, medium and low.

For Uzbekistan, studying the experience of Asian countries, which are leading in the textile industry, and analyzing their development factors in accelerating marketing activities in the international market is of great scientific and practical importance. Foreign experience shows that the combination of an active marketing system of enterprises and state support for the industry is a guarantee of a favorable marketing environment and effective marketing activities.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 11

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